

THE MANIFESTATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE TEACHERS AS A PSYCHOLOGICAL PHENOMENON

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***Abstrac.** In this article, the manifestation of professional competence in future educators as a psychological phenomenon has a wide range of theoretical and practical aspects, expressed through personal characteristics, emotional intelligence, motivation, socio-communicative abilities and social adaptation abilities of the individual.*

***Keywords:** future educators, professional competence, motivation and professional satisfaction.*

As a psychological phenomenon, professional competence develops not only the knowledge and skills of future educators, but also their interest in them and a responsible approach to their activities. As a psychological phenomenon, professional competence is considered a set of abilities that are formed in the process of personal and professional development of a person. These abilities are interconnected with the internal aspirations of the individual, the level of self-awareness, and the ability to adapt to changes in the environment. Professional competence is of deep psychological importance, especially in educational activities, since educators play an important role in the mental, moral and social development of the younger generation.

Emotional intelligence is an integral part of professional competence, since this quality develops the ability to understand and manage a person's emotions, to establish effective relationships with children and teammates. Educators with high emotional intelligence can more deeply feel the needs of children and provide them with timely psychological support. Empathy serves as the basis for the educator to establish a sincere connection with children and understand their emotional state, which makes the educational process more effective.

Professional competence is directly related to motivation and professional satisfaction. Professional motivation in future educators causes them to approach their activities with interest, to be satisfied with working with children, and to strive to fulfill their duties within the framework of their responsibilities. Professional satisfaction, in turn, strengthens the internal motivation of educators, encourages them to further develop and work on themselves.

As a psychological phenomenon, one of the main aspects of professional competence is socio-communicative ability. Through this ability, educators are able to establish effective communication with children and their parents, achieve cooperation in the educational process, and manage relationships in a positive way. This ability is important for future educators and plays a key role in solving problems that arise in the educational process.

Reflective competence, that is, the ability to analyze one's own activities and assess achievements and shortcomings, is considered important in the manifestation of professional competence. Reflective competence helps educators to regularly evaluate themselves and their pedagogical activities, work on themselves and improve their activities. This ability provides

educators with professional growth and allows them to adapt their approaches to the needs of children.

The formation and manifestation of professional competence plays an important role in the process of overall human development. Through this competence, a person develops such skills as self-management, harmonization of internal aspirations, and overcoming difficulties on the way to achieving goals. Thus, professional competence is important not only for success in professional activities, but also for success in personal life.

The manifestation of professional competence in future educators is a complex and multifaceted process as a psychological phenomenon, formed by the interaction of a person's internal abilities, emotions, motivation and social skills. This phenomenon is considered a key factor in their effective communication with children, management of the educational process and positive impact on children's development. Therefore, the development of professional competence provides not only professional growth for future educators, but also personal maturity.

Today, the issue of studying the professional development of a person, their professional abilities and level of competence poses specific tasks for a number of areas of psychology. Because in the acmeological development of a person, his professional development also plays an important role. The subject of our research, socio-psychological competence and its development, is a complex process in its own right. A similar concept has found its expression in all scientific literature, but without denying this concept, it can be said that a single scientific methodological development of the highest level has not yet been adopted for analyzing the effectiveness of professional activity solely as a criterion of socio-psychological effectiveness as a means of competence. The formation of professional competence is considered an important component of personal identity for future educators. Professional identification forms a person's attitude to his profession and supports their internal motivation. Through personal identification, educators feel a sense of belonging to a professional role, which has a positive impact on their professional activities and provides them with a unique mental flexibility aimed at successfully fulfilling their tasks.

Since the teaching profession often requires strong emotional loads, the ability to maintain emotional stability and balance is of great importance. Emotional stability helps educators manage their emotions, make effective decisions in difficult situations, and provide children with a stable mental environment. By developing this ability, future teachers can overcome the stress and difficulties they face in the educational process, which in turn increases their professional competence.

One of the important aspects of professional competence is the psychological flexibility of future educators. The educational process has constantly changing conditions, and educators must be ready to adapt to new requirements and pedagogical situations. Psychological flexibility allows educators to take into account the needs of different students, use different educational methods and develop a creative approach in their activities.

Social intelligence is important for the effective formation of professional competence. Social intelligence refers to the ability of educators to understand social situations, interact with others, and sense the emotional state of children. Educators with developed social intelligence establish effective communication with children, positively influencing their growth and development. Through this, they can establish trusting and open communication with children and form positive relationships in the educational process. In the modern education system, future

educators must have the opportunity to use innovative and creative approaches. Creative competence allows educators to introduce innovations into the educational process, solve problems using unique methods, and arouse children's interests. Through innovative approaches, educators are able to adapt their teaching methods to modern requirements, increase the level of children's mastery, and involve them in active participation in the educational process.

A comprehensive study of professional activity based on an individual approach is to look at the activity in the "labor subject-professional environment" system and determine the components under the "labor subject" and "professional environment" systems and the structure of interrelationships within these components. holds in

The "Professional environment" process, in turn, consists of the following:

- labor object and weapon.
- technology of professional activity and its subject.
- professional, organizational, physical and social conditions of professional activity, etc.

At the same time, if competence is considered as an ability, then we are talking about various abilities and talents of a person. Here we see that there are different approaches to the interpretation of the concept of "Ability".

In the functional-genetic approach, ability is interpreted as a description of the efficiency of functional systems that implement this or that mental process. In this case, the concepts of "competence" and "competency" reflecting the unity of cognitive, motivational and behavioral components in the personality structure can be considered as abilities.

According to A.V. Khutorsky, competence is an individual psychological characteristic. In our opinion, competence is not only an individual psychological characteristic, but also includes volitional qualities. Because if it were not for these volitional qualities, educators of preschool educational organizations would not have achieved success in their professional activities

A.I. Subetto analyzes the concepts of competence and competence in the range of categories of qualities, properties, skills.

A.I. Subetto notes that the concepts of competence and competence are complex structural and dynamic education, but are secondary to the categories of qualities and properties. In this regard, it is subject to the following general principles:

- the principle of the existence of a system of potential and actual external and internal contradictions in the emergence and development of quality;
- the principle of integrity and systematicity, in which the internal structure of quality determines the quality of the object at a high level of quality, and the external structure of quality determines the quality of the interaction of the object or process with the external environment at a real level of quality;
- the principle of reflecting the quality of various processes in the results.

In the study of the structure of the concepts of competence and competence, several directions can be distinguished. Many authors consider the activity approach to be promising, and they also consider competence to be manifested in professional activity and, at the same time, its basis. In this case, competence is understood as a system of internal resources necessary for the formation of effective action within a specific framework of the process. The structure of competence is divided into the following components: directional and executive, substantive (knowledge) and procedural (skills), cognitive and operational.

A.K. Osnisky noted that self-control of a person in the process of entering into activity is an ordering carried out by the subject and aimed at bringing his capabilities into line with the requirements of this activity. At the same time, such self-control does not apply to the self-ordering of human physiological functions and mental states. At the same time, within the framework of self-control of activity, a certain part of physiological self-control and self-control of mental states can also be the subject of goal-directed management related to the issues facing the subject [1].

If a person's self-control in the process of engaging in activity is not consistent with physiological control, then we will not achieve any success. When both conditions are in place, we will achieve our intended goal [1].

In pedagogical and psychological sources, special importance is attached to the following aspects of socio-psychological competence in a person:

a) a high sense of social responsibility, rational decision-making in interpersonal relationships, and tolerance in ethnic relations, which correspond to the social requirements of the person;

b) communicative-ability to communicate in written and oral forms in different languages;

c) a critical attitude to social information disseminated through the media;

g) a high need for cognitive self-improvement, the ability to activate one's own potential, self-development;

d) interethnic ethnic competencies;

e) competence in the field of independent cognitive activity;

j) preparation for independent performance of special professional activities, assessment of the results of one's own work.

Separate research is being conducted on the organizational and methodological aspects of the formation of the above competence.

The socio-psychological competence of educators of preschool educational organizations is determined by their ability to work on themselves and constructively enter into interpersonal relationships. As we noted above, the study of the laws of the formation of socio-psychological competence of educators of preschool educational organizations is of urgent importance today. Because, without studying socio-psychological competence and its factors, it is impossible to study the issue of professional competence of educators. As we know, professional competence is a set of personal abilities that determine the effectiveness of the educational process. Socio-psychological competence is an important aspect for the effective organization of the activities of preschool educational workers.

Therefore, if the educator's speech is not fluent, it will be difficult to communicate with the child in any situation. This requires the educator to have a certain level of pedagogical technique, and the mechanisms of extralinguistic influence, that is, the timbre of the voice, the specific expression of the facial expressions and the mood, must be harmonious. The educator must be organized, prone to humor, intelligent, rich in humor, and at the same time demanding of himself and those around him. The educator must behave in such a way that each of his actions is connected with upbringing, and he must be able to understand what needs to be learned from each situation.

In particular, Sh.A. Amonashvili and his students emphasize that the result of educating and educating the children depends on the personality of the educator [3]. According to the author, the effectiveness of a teacher's work is determined by individual characteristics, attention to

children, the ability to listen to them, being active and having a mechanism of influence on upbringing.

As S.D. Yakusheva's research shows, one of the most necessary personal qualities of a teacher is a system of professional values. S.D. Yakusheva proves that professional and socio-psychological competence is manifested in the knowledge, diligence, creativity, humanity, and activity of the teacher [2].

Thus, the skill of a teacher is directly related to personal qualities. This helps to implement a number of tasks. Teachers should be able to interact with each other in interpersonal relationships, introduce an atmosphere of creative cooperation in the pedagogical process, and unleash the creative potential of teachers and students in their work. The educator must pay attention to his or her own actions, emotions, mood, and ability to perceive others in communication, and be able to manage the culture of communication.

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